

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SELJUK ELEMENTS IN THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS OF GANJA OF THE 11TH-13TH CENTURIES

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Abstract

The cultural and archaeological remains from the Seljuk period represent a significant stage in the history of Islamic heritage. Many monumental works from this era are still regarded as most beautiful and impressive examples of world culture. Similarities have been observed in the artistic and architectural monuments found in territories inhabited by Turkic peoples during the Seljuk Empire, as well as in those in the neighboring Caliphate. The unity of the architectural monuments, construction methods, and decorative principles in the Islamic world is quite evident. This cohesion has led researchers to adopt terms like "Seljuk style" and "Seljuk influence."

The Azerbaijani city of Ganja, which was governed by the Seljuk rulers during the 11th to 13th centuries, emerged as a significant cultural and economic center in the Middle East. Archaeological expeditions in the city of Ganja have confirmed the presence of pottery, silk weaving, and coppersmith workshops during the Seljuk period. Excavations at the Karpijlitepe site in the Ganja-Gazakh region of Azerbaijan have uncovered elements of a feudal castle's facade, along with fragments of its walls. Archaeological excavations conducted in the 1960s along the Ganja-Baku railway, 8-10 km from the line, uncovered metal coins, ceramics, glass, and metal objects. These finds are associated with a cultural layer dating from the 9th to the 14th centuries.

Keywords: Archaeological monuments, Cultural heritage, Cities of Azerbaijan, 11th-13th centuries, History of Ganja.

Archaeological materials are a vital component of our cultural and material heritage, serving as a crucial source of historical memory. Studying cultural heritage, which includes historical monuments and archaeological artifacts, not only enriches the intellectual and spiritual lives of individuals but also reflects the values of a nation. Considering the global processes currently shaping our world, the study of ancient cities' histories, as well as their material and cultural heritage, is becoming increasingly significant. This is especially true for the archaeologically rich cities of Azerbaijan, such as Barda, Ganja, Nakhchivan, Gabala, Lerik, and Shamkir. These cities not only attract the interest of local historians but also draw the attention of archaeologists from around the globe due to their unique contributions and interactions with neighboring civilizations.

The Turkic world has long been recognized as a cradle of rich culture and civilization, profoundly influencing the course of world history. The states established by Turkic dynasties, which spanned vast territories, exemplify the unity of all Turkic peoples. The study and exploration of shared historical features among these peoples is clearly relevant for fostering stronger ties between their countries in the future.

The Seljuks ruled a significant portion of Anatolia from the early 11th century until the early 14th century, leaving behind a substantial material and cultural legacy in the territories they controlled. In the latter half of the 11th century, Southern Azerbaijan and Arran became part of the Great Seljuk state. However, in the first half of the 12th century, as the Seljuks began to weaken, the Ildegizids state (also known as the Atabegs) gained strength in Azerbaijan.

During the 11th to 13th centuries, Azerbaijani cities flourished under the Seljuk rulers, experiencing significant political, economic, and cultural growth. Archaeological excavations in Azerbaijan have revealed numerous materials that demonstrate the connections these cities had with the Caucasus, the Middle East, and various Asian countries [11, p.21]. Ganja holds a unique significance among these cities, as it is regarded as one of the largest centers in the Middle East. Important trade routes passed through this city, making it an active participant in the transit trade between the East and the West. Due to its strategically advantageous geographical position, Ganja served as the residence for many rulers and became renowned as a major cultural center during the medieval period. The 11th to 13th centuries are recognized as a time when numerous architectural monuments were built in Azerbaijan, with Ganja leading the way in this development. Professor Arif Mammadov links the cultural and economic growth of Ganja to the reign of the Ildegizids dynasty from 1136 to 1225. He points out that archaeological findings from this period demonstrate that Ganja served as a center of Azerbaijani culture [10, s.31].

The distinguished archaeologist Isag Jafarzade significantly contributed to the study of the ancient and medieval history of Ganja. He began his research in this city, where he uncovered numerous material and cultural monuments during his archaeological excavations and published his findings [16]. Moses Altman was one of the first researchers to study Ganja. In his research published in 1949, he provided valuable insights into the material and cultural monuments from the Seljuk

period that were uncovered during archaeological excavations in Ganja [12]. In subsequent years, the city's archaeological significance continued to attract the attention of several researchers, including Jalil Khalilov, Arif Mamedov, Vagif Asadov, and Shamil Najafov [20; 8;13].

The Ganja Gate (currently one of the gates is in Georgia) was built in 1063 during the reign of Abulesvar Shavur (1049-1067). He was appointed Emir of Ganja by the Seljuk ruler Alp Arslan. This gate is a significant monument from the Seljuk period. Crafted from iron and cast iron by the blacksmith Osman-oglu Ibrahim, it features Kufic inscriptions in Arabic, which are commonly found on cultural monuments from that era [13, p.16].

Archaeological excavations in the Ganja region have revealed stamps found beneath clay pots, indicating that during the 12th and 13th centuries, various craft organizations operated in Ganja—a significant center for trade, crafts, and politics. These organizations went by names such as "merchants" and "workers." It can be inferred that these seals belonged to the craftsmen or workshops responsible for producing these items [13, p.25]. For instance, a ceramic vessel inscribed with "Ahmed Abubakr oglu Ganjavi" was discovered in Ganja. Similarly, vessels found in Beylagan bear inscriptions such as "Ali Aziz oglu," "Nasr," "Khattab," "Rustam," and "Seyideli" [5, p.87].

Seljuk architecture represents a significant phase in the evolution of Islamic architecture. Many monumental structures built during the Seljuk period are still considered some of the most beautiful examples of architectural design in the world. Additionally, several elements introduced by Seljuk architects have been utilized in later architectural developments [14, p.176]. The material and cultural artifacts from this period represent a valuable heritage that highlights the talent and skill of their creators. It is important to note that the monuments from the Seljuk period possess distinct characteristics compared to the cultural monuments that came before and after them. Notably, the construction of round domes and spiral staircases are considered key elements of Seljuk architecture. The Seljuks were among the pioneering Muslim architects to utilize this type of dome and staircase design. Spiral staircases enabled architects to construct more intricate and compact buildings, while round domes were viewed as symbols of divine light and order [14, p.177]. The spiral staircase style was commonly used in the architecture of many cities in Azerbaijan in subsequent years, with examples still visible in buildings in cities such as Ganja and Baku.

The architectural monuments from the Seljuk period, particularly mosques, are worthy of special attention. Unlike the domed mosques typical of Ottoman architecture, Seljuk mosques are characterized by their long, low structures supported by numerous columns. Most buildings from this era, including mosques, madrassas, and tombs, were constructed from stone in an ascetic style and featured intricate carvings, primarily around the windows and doors. The Bibiheybat Mosque, which was restored in Baku at the end of the 20th century, is a historical monument that dates back

to the 13th century during the Elkhandid period. It showcases elements of Seljuk culture. There are differing opinions among researchers about the construction date of the Imamzadeh Mosque in Ganja. However, some scholars believe that the central part of this mosque, designed in the elongated style typical of Seljuk architecture, was built at the end of the 13th century [19, p.253]. One of the key reasons for "Seljukization" was the spread of Muslim culture and the construction of mosques across the territories unified under the political authority of the new dynasty. In this context, the increase in Muslim structures throughout the empire was directly linked to the directives issued by the Great Seljuks and their vassals.

The remains of the "Tomb of the Generous Butcher," unearthed during archaeological excavations led by Isag Gafarzade in the 1940s, are likely parts of a structure that collapsed after the 1139 Ganja earthquake [9, p.28]. It is important to note that the bridges constructed across the Ganja River during the reign of the Ildegizids (Atabegs), who selected Ganja as one of their residences, were largely destroyed by natural disasters. Today, only some remnants, including their supports and fragments, have survived. The remains of an 11th-12th century bridge were discovered during archaeological excavations carried out in 1939-1940. This bridge connected two parts of the city and was constructed using river stones, marble-like stones, and fired bricks [9, p.16].

Archaeologist Jalil Khalilov studied glazed ceramics from the 12th century and other archaeological materials found during excavations on the left bank of the city. He concluded that this area was developed after the earthquake of 1138/1139 and was not heavily populated. Khalilov supports his conclusion by noting the uneven distribution of the discovered materials, with some locations showing a complete absence of such items [19, p. 102–104]. Archaeological excavations conducted in an area of 810 hectares, divided into two sections by the Ganja River, have uncovered evidence of urban culture from various historical periods. Researchers indicate that the right bank of the river is the primary part of the city, as it contains deeper cultural layers [17, p. 57–58].

Archaeological expeditions in the medieval urban and rural settlements of the Ganja-Gazakh region in Azerbaijan, specifically in the area of Karpichlitapa, have uncovered compelling evidence of the Seljuk history of Ganja and Shamkir. The period of Karpichlitapa's development is generally regarded as spanning from the 11th to the 13th centuries. During archaeological excavations in this area, parts of a feudal castle were discovered, including elements of the castle facade and separate fragments of the castle walls. The castle walls were constructed from flat, durable natural stones and bricks, which were fired in pairs—a type of masonry typical of medieval architecture known as "Ganja masonry" [13, p. 175-176]. The use of brick was a significant characteristic of Seljuk architecture. The Seljuks are regarded as the first Muslim architects to primarily utilize brick as their main building material. This approach enabled them to construct structures with more complex and elegant designs, distinguishing

their work from early monuments made of stone [14, p.176].

Archaeological excavations in various settlements of Azerbaijan indicate that pottery art experienced significant advancements during the 9th to 13th centuries. The ceramics produced during this period were more sophisticated than in earlier times, showcasing improved production methods and decorative elements. Additionally, this era marked the beginning of the creation of clay pipes for water systems, as well as tiles and decorative bricks, which were widely utilized in construction [15, p. 57]. Clay objects decorated with various motifs, discovered during excavations, represent an intriguing category of ceramics from the 11th to 12th centuries [16]. The surfaces of these ceramics feature plant motifs, along with both polychrome and monochrome patterns. Additionally, they include various animal images, such as lions, horses, gazelles, birds, and fish. Furthermore, the excavations uncovered ceramics adorned with Arabic inscriptions and illustrations of Seljuk warriors [12]. During the 11th to 13th centuries, ceramic masters in Ganja and Shamkir commonly decorated single-handed cups with sun-shaped designs. In comparison, ceramic products from the 11th to 12th centuries primarily featured geometric and plant ornaments. However, after the 13th century, the predominant decorations shifted to include images of plants, people, and animals [3, p.60].

The 11th to 13th centuries are regarded as the peak of various crafts in Azerbaijan's cities. The presence of pottery, silk weaving, and copper workshops created opportunities to export these products to international markets [1, p.35]. Sources provide information about the development of pottery in Ganja during the 11th to 13th centuries. The 11th-century geographer Ibn Khordadbeh described the production of white clay vessels with seals on the bottom in Arran. These dishes were created both with and without decorative images, including various representations of nature and animals. Numerous vessels of this type have been uncovered during archaeological excavations in Ganja and its surrounding areas [6].

Archaeological findings from the 11th to early 13th centuries indicate a significant development in metalworking in Ganja and its surrounding areas. The metal products from this period demonstrate increased diversity and higher quality compared to previous times. Artifacts dating from the 11th to the early 13th centuries frequently include a variety of household and agricultural items made of metal, created using new technical methods, as well as industrial waste [7, p. 196]. Archaeological excavations in the Ganja region reveal that during the Seljuk period, the city had metalworking workshops and skilled artisans. These craftsmen produced metal utensils, arrows, nails, and various household items. Hamdallah Qazvini mentions the presence of iron, copper, silver, and quartz mines near Ganja [18]. Numerous metal coins discovered during archaeological excavations in Ganja and its surrounding areas suggest that metallurgy was advancing in the region. It is likely that these coins were minted and produced in designated locations. Additionally, historical

sources indicate that jewelers were active in Ganja during this time. They crafted not only decorative items but also silver bowls and dishes that were utilized at royal banquets.

During the excavations, several rare artifacts were uncovered, including exquisite bracelets, clay pots adorned with various floral patterns, and weapons made from bone and stone. Additionally, the discovery of clay pipes at the archaeological site in Karpichtepe suggests that water supply systems existed during that time. The discovered remains of various tandoors, fireplaces, wells, and agricultural pits offer valuable insights into the development of medieval Azerbaijani cities and the lifestyles of their inhabitants. Excavations have uncovered numerous copper coins minted during the reign of the Atabegs (Ildegizids) in the 11th and 12th centuries, which reveal the level of development of commodity-money relations in the medieval city of Ganja.

Archaeological excavations conducted in the 1960s along the Ganja-Baku railway line, located 8-10 kilometers from Ganja, revealed three distinct cultural layers. Archaeologists from the Ganja expedition noted that the thickness of the upper cultural layer is 1.3 meters and is believed to date back to the 9th to 14th centuries. Within this layer, 16 metal coins, along with various ceramics and glass and metal objects, were discovered [8, p.166].

With the onset of the Islamic era, a new ornamental motif began to emerge in carpet design: Koranic inscriptions. By the 9th and 10th centuries, the texts of the Koran became a fundamental element in the architecture throughout the Muslim world, including Azerbaijan. Kufic calligraphy started to appear in Azerbaijani architecture during the 12th and 13th centuries. A notable example of this style is the Momine Khatun Mausoleum, built in the 12th century. Kufic calligraphy, known for its beautiful decorative qualities, has influenced various art forms, including architecture and carpets. During the Seljuk period, Kufic Arabic calligraphy was prominently featured in carpets, enhancing their aesthetic appeal in decorative and applied art. Additionally, excerpts from the Quran began to adorn the edges of these carpets. The 13th-century Azerbaijani carpets known as "Ganja," "Shirvan," "Mugan," and "Baku" featured a decorative style that included Kufic inscriptions along the edges. These inscriptions on the carpets from this period can be compared to the remains of a 13th-century Seljuk-era carpet, which is part of the collection at the Istanbul Museum of Turkish and Islamic Arts. This particular carpet was uncovered during archaeological excavations in Turkey [6].

The Seljuk state, which encompassed various countries in Central and Western Asia as well as the entire Caucasus region, significantly contributed to the development of these areas. The history of the Seljuk period in the Caucasus shows that the 11th and 12th centuries marked a time of continuous growth for local societies. During this time, Azerbaijani cities joined the general flow of socioeconomic, political, and cultural development, becoming an integral part of the world feudal system. The peoples under the Seljuk rule made a significant contribution to world history.

Despite the Seljuk Empire's brief existence and nominal presence in some remote areas, the artistic and architectural processes of this period are unanimously recognized in the territories inhabited by Turkic peoples and the neighboring Caliphate. This unity is evident in the most notable architectural monuments, construction methods, and decorative principles of the Islamic world. This allows researchers to use expressions such as "Seljuk style" and "Seljuk influence." The emergence of the Great Seljuk Empire and the establishment of Turkish rule marked a turning point in Islamic civilization, determining the future of the Turkish and Christian worlds.

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